

PHOTOSENSITISATION BY SOLIDS. PART III. PHOTOSENSITISED OXIDATION OF AMMONIA IN AQUEOUS SOLUTION WITH COLLOIDAL TITANIA AS THE PHOTSENSITISER.

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The photosensitised oxidation of ammonia in the total ultraviolet light from the quartz-mercury vapour lamp has been studied using negatively charged colloidal titania as the photosensitiser. The rate of reaction is found to be practically unaffected by temperature and the concentration of ammonia. The decrease of reaction velocity on the addition of suitable flocculating ions shows that the reaction is a heterogeneous one. The mechanism of the reaction has been discussed.

In Part I of this series Gopalarao (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1930, **A**, 184, 377) discussed the mechanism of the photosensitisation by titania by studying the simple reaction of oxidation of ammonia. Gopalarao and Murty in a subsequent part (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1941, **18**, 127) have adduced further support for the mechanism already proposed (*vide* Part I). In the publications referred to, it was stated that the photosensitised oxidation of ammonia is a heterogeneous catalytic reaction taking place at the surface of titania under the influence of light. The ammonia adsorbed on the surface of titania interacts with the same under the influence of light, the titania being reduced to a lower oxide. The titanium dioxide is regenerated from the lower oxide by the action of atmospheric oxygen. In view of the importance of surface in this reaction it appeared to us that it would be of considerable interest to study the photosensitised oxidation of ammonia using colloidal titania as the photosensitiser.

EXPERIMENTAL.

The source of ultraviolet light is a Hereaus quartz-mercury vapour lamp worked on 220 volts D.C. at 3.0 amperes. The arc was cooled by working a fan in the neighbourhood. The light was condensed and rendered parallel with the help of a quartz condenser on to the reaction cell, which was a quartz cylindrical vessel with two plane parallel sides of diameter 4 cm. The cell was fitted with a ground-in stopper and has a capacity of 40 ml. The cell was mounted inside a thermostat provided with two windows fitted with quartz plates. Distilled water was circulated through this thermostat from another bigger thermostat of Lowry type by means of a circulating pump. Temperature was controlled to $\pm 0.1^\circ$.

Preparation of Colloidal Titania.—The methods so far developed for the preparation of hydrous titanium dioxide sol give positively charged sols. Graham prepared a hydrous titania sol by dialysis of an 1% solution of the oxide in dilute hydrochloric acid. Bhatia and Ghosh (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1930 7, 687) prepared a sol containing 15 g. of TiO_2 per litre by dropping titanium tetrachloride slowly into water at 18° followed by dialysis. Freundlich and Kross (*Kolloid Z.*, 1930, 82, 37) prepared sols, containing 440 to 640 g. per litre by hydrolysis of titanic sulphate, washing the hydrous oxide free from sulphate with ammonia, and finally peptising with as small an amount of hydrochloric acid as possible. In these sols both H^+ and Ti^{+++} are the stabilising ions. The sols are, therefore, positively charged. As positively charged sols are coagulated by the addition of dilute aqueous ammonia, the following method for the preparation of a hydrous titanium dioxide sol, containing negatively charged particles, was adopted. Merck's titanium tetrachloride was dissolved in water containing hydrochloric acid and the solution treated with excess of aqueous ammonia in the cold in order to precipitate the whole of the titanium dioxide as the so-called orthotitanic acid. The precipitate was freed from electrolytes first by decantation and then by washing repeatedly on the filter. When the wash gave no further test for chlorides, the precipitate was suspended in distilled water, contained in a stoppered Jena bottle. A small amount of "ammonia fort" was added and the bottle shaken vigorously for a long time until the hydrated titania was peptised and passed into colloidal condition. This was then filtered and carefully dialysed to free it from most of the ammonia. It was found that a small amount of ammonia was necessary for the stability of the hydrosol. This sol contains negatively charged particles and is quite stable in the presence of excess of ammonia. The concentration of the sol was determined by evaporating off a known volume of the sol in a weighed dry silica dish and strongly igniting, cooling and reweighing. The increase in weight of the dish gives the weight of titanium dioxide present in the known volume of the colloid. In this way it was found that the sol contained 0.45 g. of TiO_2 per litre.

*Photosensitised Oxidation of Ammonia in Aqueous Solution
in the total Ultraviolet Light.*

20 ml. of $N/2$ or of another strength of aqueous ammonia solution were taken in the reaction cell and 20 ml. of the hydrosol of titania added,

The cell was then closed with the stopper and the contents shaken and exposed to light from a quartz-mercury vapour lamp as already described for the requisite length of time. The exposure was then stopped, and the contents transferred into a clean conical flask. The colloidal titania was coagulated by the addition of a small quantity of pure solid barium chloride. The solution was then filtered and the nitrite content in the filtrate determined by the Griess-Ilosvay colorimetric method.

TABLE I.

Progress of reaction with time.

Temp. = 30°3'.

Time.	NO ₂ -N per litre.		Time.	NO ₂ -N per litre.	
	N/4-ammonia.	N/8-ammonia.		N/4-ammonia.	N/8-ammonia.
8 hrs.	1'22 mg.	1'06 mg.	32 hrs.	4'74 mg.	4'13 mg.
16	2'36	2'01	40	6'10	5'16
24	3'52	3'04			

Table I shows that the amount of nitrite formed increases in direct proportion to the time of exposure. In the absence of titania the amount of nitrite formed in 20 hours was found to be equivalent to 0'11 mg. of nitrite-nitrogen per litre with an N/4 solution. In the presence of titania it will be about 3'06 mg. These results clearly show the photosensitising action of titania. In the following table are recorded the results on the effect of the variation of the concentration of ammonia on the rate of reaction.

TABLE II.

Influence of concentration of ammonia.

Exposed for 10 hrs. TiO₂ = 0'0090 g. in 40 ml. soln.

Conc. of ammonia.	NO ₂ -N per litre.	Conc. of ammonia.	NO ₂ -N per litre.	Conc. of ammonia.	NO ₂ -N per litre.
$2.5 \times 10^{-1} N$	1'53 mg.	1.5625×10^{-2}	1'12 mg.	4.8828×10^{-4}	0'55 mg.
1.25×10^{-1}	1'32	7.8125×10^{-3}	1'03	2.4414×10^{-4}	0 50
0.25×10^{-1}	1'21	1.9531×10^{-3}	0'82	1.2207×10^{-4}	0 44
3.125×10^{-2}	1'15	9.7655×10^{-4}	0'76	6.1034×10^{-5}	0'41

From Table II it is evident that the photosensitised oxidation of ammonia is a reaction of zero order as the reaction rate is very nearly independent of the concentration of ammonia. Moreover, for a very large change in the concentration of ammonia, the change in the rate of reaction is only very slight. For instance, when the concentration is decreased from $2.5 \times 10^{-1}N$ to $1.562 \times 10^{-2}N$, the amount of NO_2-N formed in 10 hours changes from 1.53 mg. to 1.12 mg., a change of only 28%. If the reaction were unimolecular, it would have effected a 1600% change.

Influence of Electrolytes.

The hydrous titanium dioxide sol, used in the experiments, contained negatively charged micelle and was coagulated by addition of suitable concentrations of positive ions like K^+ , Ba^{++} , etc., obtained from their salts. It has been suggested by Gopalarao (*loc. cit.*) that the photosensitised oxidation of ammonia is a heterogeneous catalytic reaction occurring at the surface of the particles of the photosensitiser and that adsorption plays an important part. During coagulation of a sol by a neutral salt agglomeration of the smaller colloidal particles into bigger aggregates is attended with large decrease in the effective surface. As the reaction studied is a photochemical one, we should select such salts as would not interfere with the absorption of light. In the following table are reported the typical results obtained with varying concentrations of potassium and barium chlorides.

TABLE III.

10 ml. of $N/2$ ammonia solution + 10 ml. of hydrous TiO_2 sol + electrolyte solution + water to make up the total volume to 40 ml.

Exposure = 5 hrs. Temp. = 30.3° .

Electro-lyte conc.	Potassium chloride.		Barium chloride.				
	NO_2-N per litre.	Electro-lyte conc.	NO_2-N per litre.	Electro-lyte conc.	NO_2-N per litre.	Electro-lyte conc.	NO_2-N per litre.
*	0.59mg.	$37.5 \times 10^{-3}M$	0.45mg.	$5.0 \times 10^{-5}M$	0.49 mg.	$50.0 \times 10^{-5}M$	0.26 mg.
$5.0 \times 10^{-3}M$	0.59	50.0×10^{-3}	0.45	10.0×10^{-5}	0.48	75.0×10^{-5}	0.20
12.5×10^{-3}	0.58	75.0×10^{-3}	0.45	20.0×10^{-5}	0.44	10.0×10^{-4}	0.19
25.0×10^{-3}	0.51	125.0×10^{-3}	0.45	25.0×10^{-5}	0.38	25.0×10^{-4}	0.19

* When no electrolyte was used.

The results in the foregoing table show that the decrease in the extent of the surface of the photosensitiser, occasioned by the addition of electrolytes, results in a decrease in the reaction rate. With any electrolyte, increasing concentration causes a progressively diminishing rate until a steady limiting rate is attained. When this point is reached, a further increase in the concentration of the electrolyte does not produce a further diminution in the rate of oxidation. The concentration that produces the limiting rate is approximately the same with Na^+ from NaCl , K^+ from KCl and NH_4^+ from NH_4Cl . A point of great significance arising from this investigation is that the concentration of divalent ions Ba^{++} or Sr^{++} required to lower the reaction rate to the limiting value is much lower than with univalent ions like Na^+ and K^+ . Further, it is also to be noted that the limiting rate with divalent ions is lower than that reached with univalent ions.

Effect of Varying the Amount of the Photosensitiser.

In the following table are reported the results obtained, when the amount of photosensitiser was varied by taking varying volumes of the hydrous titan ia sol, while keeping the concentration of ammonia constant.

TABLE IV.

Concentration of ammonia = $N/8$. Temp. = 30.3° . Exposed for 5 hrs.

TiO_2 in 40 ml. (g.)	...	0.01350	0.01125	0.00900	0.00675	0.00450
$\text{NO}_2\text{-N}$ (mg. per litre)	...	0.54	0.62	0.71	0.57	0.53

Table IV shows that increase in the amount of the photosensitiser increases the rate of reaction up to a certain limit beyond which a further increase produces a diminishing rate of reaction. Similar results are often noticed in other photosensitised reactions by other investigators.

Temperature Coefficient of the Reaction.

The required temperature was maintained to $\pm 0.1^\circ$ by circulating water from a big Lowry type thermostat through the smaller thermostat in which the reaction cell is mounted.

TABLE V.

Conc. of ammonia = $N/8$. Photosensitiser = 0.0090 g. per 40 ml. soln.
Exposed for 8 hrs.

Temp.	Nitrite-nitrogen per litre.			
	8 hrs	16 hrs.	24 hrs.	32 hrs.
30°3'	1.06 mg.	2.01 mg.	3.04 mg.	4.13 mg.
40°3'	1.22	2.40	3.69	4.83
50°3'	1.24	2.45	3.68	4.87

The temperature coefficient $K_{40^\circ}/K_{30^\circ} = 1.2$ and $K_{50^\circ}/K_{30^\circ} = 1.0$.

D I S C U S S I O N .

The results presented in this paper support the conclusion that the photosensitised oxidation of ammonia occurs as a heterogeneous photocatalytic reaction at the surface of titania. That the extent of surface is a determining factor is shown by the fact that the rate of reaction is diminished by decreasing the surface of the colloidal titania by the addition of suitable concentrations of electrolytes. The electrolytes added agglomerate and coagulate the colloid, thereby decreasing the available surface. They also tend to displace the adsorbed ammonia from the surface of the photocatalyst. That an interfacial factor is truly operating is conclusively shown by the result that the degree of inhibition produced by univalent ion like that of Na^+ is much less than that produced by the divalent Ba^{++} ion. A heterogeneous photochemical reaction, though very interesting because of its novelty, is somewhat complex and presents a variety of interesting aspects from the theoretical standpoint. We have to take into account the adsorption of ammonia on the surface of the photocatalyst, the spectral sensitivity of the photocatalyst, the intensity of the light, etc.

In Part II of this series it has been shown that ammonia is very tenaciously adsorbed by titania. When adsorption is strong it will be noticed from the Langmuir adsorption isotherm

$$U = \frac{K_2 C}{K_1 C + 1}$$

that when, C , the concentration of ammonia is high, $K_1 C$ will be very large compared to unity so that the amount adsorbed,

$$U = \frac{K_2 C}{K_1 C} = \frac{K_2}{K_1} = \text{constant.}$$

Now the velocity of the reaction will be proportional to the active mass of the substance adsorbed and hence in a position to react. When adsorption is strong it is seen that the amount adsorbed is practically constant and independent of the concentration of the ammonia in the solution. Hence the reaction velocity should also be independent of the concentration of ammonia in the solution; in other words, the reaction should exhibit the characteristics of a zero molecular reaction. That this is the case is shown by the results recorded in Table II.

Increasing the surface of the heterogeneous catalyst by increasing the amount of colloidal titania also increases the speed of the reaction up to a certain limit as shown by the results in Table IV. This fact also indicates a possible chemical reaction between the photosensitiser and ammonia. Moreover, it has been shown that the formation of nitrite from ammonia occurs in the presence of titania even in the complete absence of oxygen.

A molecule of titania on the surface gets activated due to absorption of a quantum of radiation. The photoactivated titania then oxidises ammonia to nitrous acid, getting itself reduced to titanous oxide Ti_2O_3 or TiO . The titanous oxide then undergoes rapid oxidation by the dissolved oxygen, thus regenerating the photosensitiser. For this reaction to occur there must be an intimate association between the molecules of the photosensitiser and ammonia, and this association is secured by adsorption.

That photoactivated titania possesses marked oxidising properties is indicated by the work of Benrath (*Z. wiss. Photochem.*, 1915, 14, 217) and Benrath and Obladen (*ibid.*, 1922, 22, 65) who showed that titanium dioxide is reduced in light in the presence of alcohol or oxalic acid. Renz (*Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1921, 4, 961) also showed that while titanium dioxide alone is stable towards light, it becomes markedly photosensitive in the presence of organic substances, particularly glycerol. Goodeve and Kitchener (*Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1938, 34, 1) concluded from a study of the fading of "Chlorazol sky Blue FF" adsorbed on titanium dioxide in the presence of light from the quartz-mercury vapour lamp, that the rate of bleaching of the dried sample exposed in vacuum is the same as that of the undried sample in the presence of air. Their results indicate that the bleaching of

the dye is a process of oxidation by titanium dioxide under the influence of light.

The mechanism here proposed for the photosensitisation by titania is similar to the "carrier-type" of mechanism suggested for some photosensitisers from time to time (*cf.* the mechanism proposed for the sensitised decomposition of oxalate in the presence of ferric chloride as sensitiser, "Photoprocesses in Gaseous and Liquid systems," Longmans, Green and Co., London, 1929).

In recent years Goodeve and co-workers have devoted considerable attention to photosensitisation by titanium dioxide (*Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1937, 33, 340; 1938, 34, 570, 902). They have tried to explain the mechanism of the photosensitisation by solids making use of the concept of "exciton" introduced by Frenkel (*Physikal. Z.Sowiet*, 1936, 9, 156).

"A quantum of energy, when absorbed by an electron in a crystal, is probably initially localised (in the case of non-conductors). Before it can cause a photochemical change, this energy must pass as a more or less complete unit (Frenkel has termed this unit an 'exciton') to the point of contact of the potentially reactive molecular species. In the case of carbon black, or metallic blacks (conductors), such a transfer is exceedingly unlikely to occur owing to disturbance of the free electrons which would lead to degradation of the "exciton" to heat. In a pure crystal of a non-conductor an excited electron is only influenced by electrons of neighbouring molecules and there is very little coupling with the vibrations of the atoms and molecules. Degradation to heat is, therefore, less likely to occur than with carbon black. Two things may happen. The "exciton" may be reradiated as fluorescence of the same or a lower frequency, or it may be passed to a neighbouring electron by resonance between the two. The probability of the transfer of energy between two electrons of identical frequencies separated by the distances occurring in crystals is high. We have, therefore, as a picture of the probable state of affairs subsequent to absorption of a light quantum, a rapid passage of the exciton at random throughout the crystal until it meets a surface where it might cause a chemical change. The "exciton" here is pictured as an excited electronic state, the energy being handed on without actual transfer of the electrons. It may, however, be of the type of excitation found in some photoconductive crystals (*cf.* Hughes, *Rev. Modern Phys.*, 1936, 8, 294) in which "an ion pair is formed on absorption of light. The positions of the ions (not the ions themselves) may move to the surface, causing oxidation or reduction."

" Many photosensitised reactions take place on the surface of the solid particles, and if an exciton is to produce a photochemical change it must diffuse to this surface. As the diffusion, however, will presumably not have a directional effect towards the surface it will usually travel a distance much greater than that between the original absorption centre and the surface. The exciton may move more readily along a particular axis of the crystal corresponding to greater interaction between the electrons in this direction."

Goodeve imagines the existence of potentially reactive centres on the surface. " A potentially reactive centre consists of a group of atoms which can undergo rearrangement or give up or accept electrons, when provided with the necessary energy. If the equilibrium position of some nucleus changes markedly in the presence of an exciton a rearrangement of atoms may readily be produced when the exciton reaches the potentially reactive centre. On the other hand if the exciton corresponds to a free electron it could readily cause a reduction on reaching a centre on the surface capable of accepting an electron."

In our view it is not necessary to assume the operation of the complex and speculative concept of " exciton " of Frenkel to explain the mechanism of photosensitisation by titanium dioxide. The experimental data of Goodeve and Kitchener (*loc.cit.*) as also the results of Gopal Rao and co-workers can be explained on the simple basis that the surface molecules only of the titanium dioxide particles are photo-active, whilst the interior molecules of titania are completely inactive. An ion of Ti^{++++} in a molecule of TiO_2 on the surface of a particle of titania gets electronically excited on the absorption of a quantum of light. An electron is raised to a higher energy level and according to Franck and Haber (*Sitz. Preuss. Akad. Wiss.*, 1931, 250) such a molecule, atom or ion which possesses an unoccupied electronic level has a tendency to take up an electron ; hence it will exert an oxidising action on substances that are adsorbed on the surface, the molecules or atoms of which donate electrons and get oxidised. Oxidation primarily consists in loss of electrons and reduction in a gain of electrons.

That the absorption of light by titania is due to a titanium ion which is raised to an excited level is made probable by the observation of Goodeve and Kitchener (*Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1938, **34**, 902) that the threshold of absorption for solid titania lies in the same region of the spectrum as that of the ions in solution.

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